

PRINCIPLES OF CREATING DIDACTIC MATERIALS USED IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of didactic materials to increase pupils' interest in the lesson and develop their thinking gives good results. The difference between non-traditional lessons, which use different forms of didactic materials, and ordinary lessons is that the teacher organizes the lesson as a game and can take children to different imaginary worlds, fairy tales and space.

Key words: scientific and pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, didactic materials, media technologies, innovative activities, interdisciplinary integration, distance learning.

INTRODUCTION

The development of didactic materials used in primary education is based on certain principles. Didactic and special-methodical principles in the creation of didactic materials help to ensure the consistency, consistency and continuity of the educational process.

1. The principle of educational nature of educational materials.

Didactic materials used in the process of primary education to educate students in the spirit of adherence to democratic ideas, humanity, mutual assistance, the priority of national and universal values, the national idea, respect for our traditions, human, society and should focus on harmonizing the interactions of the environment and ensure that this is reflected in the content of the training materials.

2. The principle of comprehensibility and fun in the design of educational materials.

Today's advances in science and technology have had a significant impact on the content of educational materials, their size and expression. Therefore, in the design of biology textbooks, authors should implement the scientific principle of education in accordance with the principle of comprehensibility and interest. That is, to ensure the

comprehensibility and interest of the information, the content of the textbook, the volume, the meaning of the sentences, questions and assignments should be clear and understandable.

3. The principle of regularity and consistency in the design of educational materials.

Ensuring the continuity of textbooks involves ensuring that the scientific concepts and rules specific to a particular topic are derived from the content of a previously learned topic, and that efforts are made to expand the information.

Consistency in the design of textbooks will ensure that the concepts initially formed by students are broadened and enriched in the pre-high school period, depending on their age and psychological characteristics.

4. The principle of unity of theory and practice in the design of educational materials.

The principle of unity of theory and practice plays an important role in the creation of didactic materials. Adherence to the principle of teaching theory in practice allows the student to gain in-depth knowledge, to perform various practical tasks independently, to develop learning skills and abilities, to organize labor education.

5. The principle of forming a scientific worldview in the use of educational materials.

When creating elementary school textbooks, special attention is paid to the fact that each teaching material is aimed at developing students' scientific understanding. Emphasis should be placed on expressing the nature of the problems with scientific evidence and helping to shape their scientific outlook by being able to scientifically analyze events and processes occurring in nature and the environment.

6. The scientific principle of creating didactic materials.

When creating textbooks for primary school, special attention is paid to the scientific basis of the information, based on the content of the textbook. It takes into account the age, level of education and psychological characteristics of students. Emphasis is placed on the development of information from easy to difficult, from simple to complex, based on pedagogical requirements. This principle requires an analysis of the nature of the original sources of knowledge expressed in the content of the study materials and a chronological approach to the process.

7. Systematic principle of designing didactic materials.

In order to master the basics of science, teaching materials must be presented to students in a systematic way. In the systematic design of teaching materials, each scientific rule is based on the previous rules, and the idea put forward in the next rule is further developed.

8. The principle of continuity and continuity.

Ensuring continuity and continuity in the design of textbooks is based on the content of the subjects taught in the types of education system. That is, the learning materials learned in the primary grades should serve as a basis for the next stage and complement each other.

9. The principle of stratification and individualization of education.

Involves the design of learning materials in accordance with the principle of stratification of education, taking into account the abilities and capabilities of students in the classroom. A differentiated and individualized approach to the selection of educational materials envisages the creation of conditions for talented young people to acquire a high level of education, consistent and fundamental knowledge.

10. The principle of vitality in the creation of educational materials.

When designing biology textbooks, it is important to focus on the content of the science, the facts, the examples, and the events and processes that occur in everyday life.

11. The principle of student activation.

Orienting students to independent activities in the creation of textbooks is important in activating their learning activities. In particular, it is advisable to set independent assignments on specific topics, as in the process of performing the assigned tasks independently, they become more interested in learning, and as a result, they become more active.

METHODS

Specific principles are derived from the specifics of the primary education process. They are:

The principle of using local materials in the design of educational materials.

During the years of independence, it has been possible to enrich the content of textbooks with information that reflects the essence of national traditions, values and historical heritage.

Adherence to this principle in the creation of educational material creates favorable conditions for students to gain a thorough knowledge of nature, national mentality, material and spiritual values.

The principle of demonstration in the creation of didactic materials.

The use of visual aids in designing the content of primary school textbooks allows students to develop a clear idea of an event, thing or process, develop their cognitive and thinking skills, and increase cognitive activity.

The following requirements should be observed when planning the use of visual aids in the design of teaching materials for primary school textbooks: and be able to create the necessary conditions for independence; 2) appropriate and moderate use of visual aids; 3) systematically use a variety of visual aids on a specific topic in multiple textbooks; 4) to develop a system of visual aids in connection with the representation of educational materials with the help of visual aids. Organizing educational activities based on the combination of oral and visual aids allows you to successfully solve many complex problems in the educational process.

I. The principle of modeling the creation of educational materials.

Modeling has long been one of the most important principles of scientific knowledge. Although the concept of "model" began to be used in the XIX century, it became popular only in the XX century.

The encyclopedic dictionary defines a model from a general point of view as follows: image, description, scheme, graph, plan, map, etc.).

A model idea represents a specific relationship of an imaginary or existing concrete system to another system, and it is expressed under the following conditions:

1. There is a similar relationship between the model and its original, in which the shape of the object is clearly expressed and clearly marked.
2. The model acts as an object of study in the process of scientific knowledge.
3. Exploring the essence of the model allows you to get enough information about the real, object.

While modeling is a meaningful principle, it is comprehensive and serves the following purposes: 1) heuristic (allows to classify the essence of new laws, the structure of new theories, as well as to interpret the data obtained); 2) calculation (calculation creates conditions for solving problems using models); 3) experimental (provides solutions to the problems of empirical verification of ideas using one or another model). Models are divided into material and intellectual (ideal) models, depending on the nature of the object.

Ideological models can be divided into iconic, symbolic, and special figurative.

Special figurative models include schemes, graphs (topographic and geographical maps), chemical formulas and drawings.

CONCLUSION

Today, "symbolic" models are widely used to express the essence of events using descriptive mathematical symbols. These include graphs, pictures, diagrams, words, tables, formulas, and symbols that represent the essence of an event or law.

Symbolic models use special symbols to describe the process by which an object or event changes. In certain models, the data is copied using schematic rules.

Trying to learn with all the complexities of a particular object without any simplification is a much more difficult task. Refusing to study the non-existent properties of the object under study is one of the prerequisites for modeling aimed at exploring any object and identifying new relationships. Most importantly, the model embodies the relationships that occur with the participation of a particular biological object in the eyes of the reader. This justifies the representation of a specific object (model) on an auxiliary basis. Theory is also seen as a model to some extent, but knowledge and thinking are infinite. The use of modeling in the design of learning materials enhances students' learning activities. As a result, the whole class, even indifferent students, begin to study the material with interest and voluntarily. Abstract imaginations are defined as a result of the student's understanding of the nature of a wide range of natural phenomena and processes that are difficult to imagine.

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